

Deliverable 3.2

Identification of potential PCI

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No industry has committed at this stage to implement the scenarios presented in the deliverable D3.2. The scenario presented here, while based on an industrial reality, is a forward-looking scenario that explores the potential of CCUS in the Baltic region.

Executive summary

The CCUS ZEN project is a European initiative to promote the deployment of Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) technologies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. With a focus on the Baltic and Mediterranean Sea regions, the project evaluates the technical and non-technical aspects of potential CCUS value chains, selecting promising sites for eventual full-scale deployment.

The document summarises work from the CCUS ZEN project's Task 3.2 of Work Package 3, discussing the requirements and advantages of obtaining Project of Common Interest (PCI) status. The classification as a PCI is crucial for vital energy infrastructure projects within the EU, supporting the European goal for climate neutrality by 2050 by interconnecting energy systems of Member States, enhancing market competition, and securing energy supply.

The report identifies potential CCUS infrastructure candidates for PCI and lists the main factors that set them in line with the Trans-European Networks for Energy (TEN-E) Regulation.

The proposed PCIs can be crucial to integrate key energy markets within the EU and benefit from faster permit processing, better regulatory conditions, and potential eligibility for financial support through the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF). The benefits extend to reduced administrative costs and the provision of a solid foundation for cross-border carbon dioxide network development. The report lists three potential PCI projects, selected from the outcome of the CCUS ZEN Work Package 3 analyses, which could highly contribute for the European overall industrial decarbonisation:

- A cross border pipeline system connecting Germany to Denmark which could transport 7.4 Mt/y of CO₂ through 205 km from emitters in Hannover and Hamburg for geological storage and utilisation in Jutland or the Danish section of the North Sea.
- A pipeline system connecting Northern Poland and Southern Eastern Lithuania to the Port of Gdańsk, transporting approximately 9 Mt/y of CO₂. The pipeline network could stretch up to 932 km and opens pathways for CCUS implementation to the Czech industry. From the Port of Gdańsk, CO₂ can be shipped for geological storage in multiple regions in the North Sea.
- A pipeline infrastructure and harbour terminal for CCUS in Southern Italy. The pipeline system connects multiple emitters in Italy while a harbour in Brindisi allows for imports of CO₂ from multiple regions, particularly Greece. The transportation infrastructure suggested for PCI would process 3 Mt/y.

The document suggests an initial stakeholder assessment, for the Baltic and Mediterranean Sea regions' proposed infrastructure projects. It also provides insight into existing EU PCIs that relate to CCUS initiatives, drawing parallels and inferring suitability for new applications. To enhance the prospects of PCI application, the report accentuates the need for multi-stakeholder collaboration, mature project definition, technical preparation, and secure financing – all aimed at demonstrating project viability and alignment with the EU energy transition objectives.

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of the project is to explore the potential for enabling CCUS value chain deployment in two regions with lower maturity level for CCUS compared to the current development in the North Sea region. The two selected regions are the Baltic Sea region and the Mediterranean Sea region.

The CCUS ZEN mission is to contribute to the accelerated deployment of CCUS throughout Europe by enabling mutual, continuous learning between different stakeholder types and between European regions, drawing on learnings from ongoing and past projects, creating shared understanding of mission-critical implementation elements that need to work like clockwork, and building a coherent ecosystem of CCUS actors in Europe that are capable of delivering the requested contribution to European climate policy.

To achieve this, CCUS ZEN has five objectives:

1. **Technical mapping:** For each region, map and understand the nature and longevity of emission sources, identify transport corridors and modalities, assess cost-effective ('bankable') storage capacity in the selected regions, and define interactions between CCUS hubs-and-clusters, renewable-based integrated energy systems, and/or circular production modes.
2. **Non-technical mapping:** Identify and involve relevant end users, public authorities and social stakeholders and analyse their concerns and needs using appropriate techniques and methods from the social sciences and humanities.
3. **Value chain scenarios:** Elaborate detailed plans for the integration of CCUS in hubs and clusters linked to CO₂ storage sites via hubs, pipeline networks and shipping routes, with due attention to national and border-crossing permits and regulatory issues.
4. **Local business model:** Perform initial impact assessments and develop local business models for delivery of CO₂ capture, transport, utilisation and/or storage, including the separation of responsibilities across the CO₂ value chain.
5. **Knowledge sharing, dissemination, and communication:** Facilitate the exchange of knowledge and know how across CCUS projects, by continuing the activities of the existing European CCUS project network.

The five objectives are integrated in the project framework illustrated in Figure 1-1. Technical and non-technical mapping constitute a high-level regional screening of CCUS opportunities in the two CCUS ZEN regions. This is followed by a selection and analyses of four promising value chains in each region studied. Based on the analyses, the most promising CCUS value chain in each region were selected for further development, including local business models. Throughout the project, the work is supported by knowledge sharing, dissemination and communication with network partners and other relevant stakeholders.

A high-level technical mapping was conducted for the two regions as presented in D1.1 [1]. This report covered technical mapping of emission sources, storage sites, transport infrastructure, utilisation options and renewables. Thereafter, CCUS value chains both in the Baltic region and Mediterranean area were defined, and in the end the eight most promising sites were selected as shown in report D1.2 [2].

Figure 1-1 CCUS ZEN framework for CCUS value chain development

This document is the second deliverable within Work Package 3 of the CCUS ZEN project. This deliverable explores the criteria for obtaining Project of Common Interest (PCI) status, outlines the benefits of achieving this designation, and provides examples of existing EU PCIs relevant to CCUS. It is important to denote the fact that the examples provided are suggestions for the development of a market that is not yet mature, and therefore, uncertainties could deviate the project outcomes from what is proposed. This report was developed in parallel with deliverable D3.1 [3] and focuses on identifying new infrastructure projects with the potential to obtain PCI status. It conducts a high-level PCI assessment based on the Trans-European Networks for Energy (TEN-E) requirements and suggests recommendations for the application to obtain PCI status. Furthermore, it details and assesses the stakeholders in the involved regions, their involvement, and roles in the suggested PCIs. The level of definition of the projects presented leads to an omission of varied factors also important for obtaining a PCI status, such as cost and economic modelling, funding, or risk assessment.

2 The European Union Project of Common Interest (PCI)

Projects of Common Interest (PCIs) serve as critical energy infrastructure that interconnect the systems across European Union member states. These projects play a crucial role in propelling the EU towards its ambitious aim of carbon neutrality by 2050, primarily by enhancing the links of the EU energy and carbon dioxide markets, which boosts energy reliability and intensifies market competition. PCIs significantly contribute to the development of transnational infrastructure, thereby providing substantial advantages in pursuit of the EU's energy transition objectives.

The PCI status is a classification that is assigned to significant energy or carbon dioxide infrastructure projects within EU, which aims to provide reliable, cost effective, and sustainable energy to EU countries.

The selection of PCIs takes place biennially, involving a comprehensive process steered by multi-faceted Regional Groups. These groups are composed of qualified delegates from the European Commission, the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER), and National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs). The Northern Lights initiative is a notable PCI example — it establishes a commercial route facilitating the maritime transfer of captured CO₂ to an offshore geological storage site in Norway.

The legal framework for the PCIs is outlined by the TEN-E regulation [4], which was established to prioritise consistency with sustainable energy objectives. As of 2022, the TEN-E Regulation shifts the support for fossil fuel infrastructure to focus on cross-border sustainable energy infrastructure. The revised TEN-E Regulation has a goal to create a market for cross-border carbon dioxide networks and hydrogen related projects.

2.1 Requirements and Criteria for Obtaining PCI Status

The requirements for obtaining the PCI status are outlined in Article (4) of the TEN-E Regulation [4], which states the following general requirements:

- The project must be necessary for at least one of the energy infrastructure priority corridors and thematic areas, as per Annex I in the TEN-E Regulation. Cross-border carbon dioxide network development is one of these priority thematic areas.
- The overall potential benefit of the project outweighs its costs.
- The project must involve at least two Member States.

Moreover, the TEN-E Regulation states specific criteria for projects falling under a specific energy infrastructure.

- Market integration, by reducing energy infrastructure bottlenecks, increase competition, interoperability, and system flexibility.
- Security of supply, by interoperability, system flexibility, cybersecurity, and reliable system operation.
- Contribute significantly to sustainability through the reduction of carbon dioxide emissions in the connected industrial installations by maintaining security of supply, increase the resilience and security of transport and storage of CO₂, and efficient use of resources by enabling multiple CO₂ sources and storage sites via common infrastructure that minimise the environmental burden and risk.
- For carbon dioxide projects, the project is used to transport and, where applicable, store anthropogenic carbon dioxide originating from at least two Member States.

The current report focuses the analyses on the market integration of different stakeholders that could take part in the CCUS value chains, contribution to sustainability, in terms of progress to national and EU decarbonisation targets, and cross border impacts that ease the

regulation difference between multiple countries to facilitate the establishment of CCUS networks. Although a limited set of criteria is analysed, these provide a good suggestion of how potential PCI projects can contribute to a cohesive and European level CCUS infrastructure.

2.2 Potential Benefits of the PCI status

Achieving the PCI status is desirable for project promoters, as it carries several benefits for projects:

- Accelerated permit granting process, enabling efficient implementation of important projects.
- Improved regulatory conditions, encouraging transparency, investor trust and facilitating the development of projects.
- Lower administrative costs through streamlined environmental assessment processes.
- Eligible for the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), which encompasses financial support for feasibility studies and construction.

The TEN-E Regulation, [4], stipulates the process and criteria for a project to be considered a PCI within any of its prioritised corridors spanning thematic areas. Within the CCUS scope, it defines the thematic area as:

“Cross-border carbon dioxide network: development of infrastructure for transport and storage of carbon dioxide between Member States and with neighbouring third countries of carbon dioxide capture and storage captured from industrial installations for the purpose of permanent geological storage as well as carbon dioxide utilisation for synthetic fuel gases leading to the permanent neutralisation of carbon dioxide.”

It provides a comprehensive framework outlining the requirements candidate projects must meet to attain PCI status.

2.3 List of relevant existing EU PCI

Table 2-1 provides an overview of existing and planned EU PCIs, which have a direct or indirect relation to Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS), as well as other sustainable energy infrastructure projects.

Table 2-1 List of relevant existing EU PCI, [5]

Project Name	Country	Applicable to CCUS ZEN	Description
Norne	Denmark, Sweden, Belgium, and United Kingdom	Potential links	Transport infrastructure in Denmark with onshore and possibly offshore storage, emitters primarily from DK, SE, BE and UK will transport to DK via ship.

D3.2 Identification of potential PCI

Project Name	Country	Applicable to CCUS ZEN	Description
Bifrost	Denmark, Germany, and Poland	Potential links	Transport and storage project with offshore storage in DK from emitters from Denmark, Germany, and Poland
Callisto	France, Italy	Potential links	Development of multi-modal CO ₂ hubs in the Mediterranean storing CO ₂ emissions from France and Italy.
Pycasso	France, Spain	Potential links	Transport and storage of CO ₂ in onshore storage site in southwestern FR, industrial emitters from FR and ES.
Prinos	Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, and Slovenia	Potential links	Offshore storage at Prinos field for emissions from EL, by pipeline, and from BG, HR, CY, EL, IT and SI by ship.
ECO2CEE	Poland, Lithuania, Czechia	Potential links	Extension/replacement of "Poland – EU CCS Interconnector" (no. 12.9 on the fifth PCI list) – open-access cross-border CO ₂ transport to and from port of Gdańsk terminal (via ship) to storage sites under the North Sea in Denmark, Norway, Netherlands, and UK.
CCS BALTIC	Latvia, Lithuania	Potential links	The CCS Baltic Consortium consists of Akmenės cementas AB, KN Energies, AB, Larvik Shipping AS, Mitsui O.S.K. Lines, Ltd. and SCHWENK Latvija SIA. 1.5 Mt CO ₂ will be captured at cement plants operated by Schwenk Latvija (LV) and Akmenės Cementas (LT) and transported by rail (or trucks) to multimodal LCO ₂ terminal in Klaipeda Port. From Klaipeda it will be transported to offshore storage site (not yet defined).
Hydrogen interconnector Spain – France (currently known as BarMar)	Spain, France	Aligned with sustainability goals and Zero Emission Network (ZEN) principles.	Hydrogen subsea pipeline connecting Spain and France.
Internal hydrogen infrastructure in France connecting to Germany (currently known as HyFen)	France	Aligned with sustainability goals and Zero Emission Network (ZEN) principles.	HY-FEN is aimed at developing a hydrogen transport infrastructure from the south of France to the German border, in continuation of the BarMar project, connecting the Iberian Peninsula, France and Germany via high-potential hydrogen valleys along its route in the Rhône valley, including major hydrogen storage projects.

Table 2-1 shows also links between the CCUS ZEN project and existing PCIs, i.e. PCIs which are similar or can potentially be included in the scope of selected CCUS networks developed within the ZEN project.

The projects proposed in section 3 can be compared to the projects listed in Table 2-1, to infer their suitability for a PCI application.

3 Overview of proposed infrastructures for PCI

This section outlines proposed infrastructure projects as candidates for PCIs that are focused on CCUS. The regions and the locations of the suggested PCI candidates under consideration are shown in Figure 3-1. There are four primary regions, each evaluated based on key criteria to ensure compliance with TEN-E regulations and to measure their contribution toward the EU's climate neutrality goal by 2050.

The proposed PCIs in this deliverable are listed in Table 3-1. Detailed assessments of each infrastructure project are provided in subsequent subsections.

Table 3-1 Proposed Infrastructures for PCI

No	PCI name	Infrastructure type	Total transported, CO ₂ , high scenario (Mt/y)
1	Cross-Border Pipeline Infrastructure: Germany-Denmark Link	Pipeline	7.2
2	Cross-border pipeline infrastructure to Port of Gdansk from Lithuania and national pipeline infrastructure to Port of Gdansk in Poland	Pipeline	9
3	Cross-border Pipeline and harbour Infrastructure: Southern Italy-Greece Link	Pipeline / harbour	19.3
4	Harbour and offshore pipeline infrastructure in Tarragona	Pipeline / harbour	9.8

The aim of the project selection for potential PCI is to study different strategies for the establishment of a CO₂ network in different regions of the EU. It is not an exhaustive list of projects with good chances of obtaining the PCI status. The selection of Table 3-1 follows the following paths:

- The PCI no. 1 divides a large network of potential CO₂ infrastructure and focuses on a fraction of it. For example, it follows a different strategy from the Bifrost PCI (see Table 2-1) and focuses on a limited amount of assets (slightly similarly to the Norne PCI), making the project financing and development simpler. It supports part of the development of a full pipeline network.
- The PCI no. 2 consists of a network of pipelines covering multiple countries. It aims to look at a full-scale development of a CO₂ pipeline network (similarly to the Bifrost PCI), leading to a holistic and wide range project.
- The PCI no. 3 combines multiple transportation methods to establish a CCUS value chain between Italy and Greece.

An additional PCI is proposed in section 3.4 at a lower level of detail, which was also studied in various stages of the CCUS ZEN project, involving France and Spain.

Figure 3-1: The two regions explored by CCUS ZEN: the Baltic Sea (green) and the Mediterranean (orange) as per D1.1 [1], with the locations of suggested PCIs highlighted in red.

3.1 Cross-Border Pipeline Infrastructure: Germany-Denmark Link

Project Name: Export pipeline from Krempermoor to Billund (Germany to Denmark)

Location: Northern Germany to Southern Denmark

Involved Member States: Germany, Denmark

Capacity: 7.4 Mt/y (estimated capacity after Phase 2 defined in D3.1, [3])

Length: 205 km

Figure 3-2 Map of Proposed PCI Infrastructure in Baltic 2 region. The proposed pipeline PCI is highlighted in green within the red dashed ellipse, with an approximated length 205 km.

The pipeline infrastructure project, extending from Krempermoor, Germany, to Billund, Denmark, aims to connect emission clusters primarily associated with power generation and cement factories in Germany to permanent geological storage sites in Denmark. In this scenario, the Hannover and Hamburg selected industrial clusters in Germany will be linked via a pipeline backbone connection with the purpose of transporting CO₂ in supercritical/dense phase to Denmark.

The two distinct emission scenarios, based on the likelihood for CCUS implementation, are categorised as low and high scenarios.

In the low scenario (Phase 1), primarily incorporating emitter clusters from Hannover and Hamburg, predominantly in power generation and cement manufacturing, individual emitters contribute between 0.55 to 1.29 Mt of CO₂ annually. The total CO₂ captured and transported in this scenario is 4.0 Mt/y.

In the high scenario (Phase 2), emissions from various industrial sectors across Hannover and Hamburg, including power generation, cement production, energy from waste, and

hydrogen manufacturing, are considered. There are 5 emitters in the Hannover cluster, and 4 in the Hamburg cluster, totalling 9 emitters. The collective potential of captured and transported CO₂ in this scenario is estimated at 7.4 Mt CO₂ per year. The captured CO₂ can be stored in the 8 storage locations identified in Denmark with an estimated capacity of 15.1 Mt/y or consumed in CCU installations in Denmark with an estimated capacity of 1.7 Mt/y.

Through the establishment of this pipeline infrastructure, the project aims to facilitate the efficient transportation of CO₂ emissions from German industrial hubs to secure geological storage sites in Denmark, contributing significantly to regional emission reduction efforts.

The proposed pipeline system for PCI certification is inserted in a conceptual pipeline network connecting Denmark to adjacent countries and storage sites within its area. Sections of this network are in development while some have already obtained a PCI certification such as Norne or Bifrost (listed in Table 2-1).

The development of the proposed pipeline from Figure 3-2 is estimated to be achievable within a period of approximately 6 years. This includes the engineering, permitting and construction works. Nonetheless, to consummate the PCI purpose, upstream capture and downstream storage sites and utilisation installations should be available as well. This will require a longer timeline for development.

3.1.1 Contribution to Market Integration

The export pipeline from Krempermoor to Billund enhances market integration by facilitating the continuous transportation of CO₂ across borders within the EU. By connecting various CO₂ emitting clusters in Germany to Denmark's infrastructure, it promotes streamlined transactions and encourages collaboration among stakeholders. Furthermore, it encourages the construction of a common cross-border regulatory framework for the carbon market and supports the decarbonisation of the respective industries that use a CCUS solution.

The project aligns with the European Union's objectives for Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) by providing a crucial infrastructure for the transportation of captured CO₂. It supports the EU's efforts to mitigate carbon emissions and transition towards a more sustainable energy system.

The evaluation of potential emitters in D3.1 [3] reveals that significant contribution could be from power production sector. The second largest sector for contributing is cement production. The full list of possible emitters exporting CO₂ via the proposed pipeline link between Germany and Denmark is outlined in Table 3-2. The list does not include CO₂ imports or captured by other regions of Germany, which could also benefit from the utilisation of the presented pipeline infrastructure.

Furthermore, the pipeline infrastructure proposed for PCI supports the supply of CO₂ to Denmark which can potentiate the development of CCU infrastructure as presented in Table 3-3. This project suggested a cluster hub in Aalborg which harbours five CCU installations to produce methanol and synthetic jet fuel. Part of the CO₂ used for this purpose can be supplied from Germany through the proposed pipeline system.

Table 3-2 Selected emitters in Germany. (*) Emissions assumed to be converted to biogenic after retrofit to biofuels. (Information from D3.1 [3])

Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Captured biogenic CO ₂ (Mt/y)
S_DE_53	Gkh - Gemeinschaftskraftwerk Hannover GmbH	Hannover	Power	1.29	1.29*
S_DE_82	Kraftwerk Mehrum GmbH	Hannover	Power	0.83	-
S_DE_116	Heidelbergcement Ag Zementwerke Hannover	Hannover	Cement	0.61	0.05
S_DE_124	Holcim (Deutschland) GmbH Werk Höver	Hannover	Cement	0.55	0.05
S_DE_130	Enertec Hameln GmbH	Hannover	Energy from waste	0.52	0.35
S_DE_62	Wärme Hamburg GmbH Heizkraftwerk Tiefstack	Hamburg	Power	1.06	1.06*
S_DE_70	Zementwerk Lägerdorf	Hamburg	Cement	1.00	-
S_DE_72	HKW (CHP) Wede	Hamburg	Power	1.00	0.00
S_DE_123	Dow Deutschland Anlagenges. MbH Werk Stade	Hamburg	Hydrogen	0.56	0.07
Total				7.4	4.0

Table 3-3 CCU suggested installations impacted by the proposed pipeline for PCI

Country	Cluster acting as collection hub	Captured CO ₂ from all emitters. (Mt/y)	Captured CO ₂ from all emitters for CCU (Mt/y)	Number of CCU installations close to the collection hub	Average capture capacity of CCU installation [kt/y]	Average product capacity of CCU installation [kt/y]
Denmark	Aalborg	5.53 <i>(from which 1.82 Mt/y biogenic)</i>	1.66	5	332	232 (for methanol) 100 (for synthetic jet fuel)

Table 3-4 Geological storage locations

Site name	Type	Location	Mean capacity (Mt)	Injectivity (Mt/y)
Gassum	Deep Saline Aquifer	Onshore	146	3.0
Voldum	Deep Saline Aquifer	Onshore	213	3.0
Jammerbugt	Deep Saline Aquifer	Nearshore	100	3.0
Inez	Deep Saline Aquifer	Offshore	178	3.0
Bifrost	Depleted O&G field	Offshore	Min. 60	0.8
Greensand	Depleted O&G field	Offshore	Min. 128	1.5
Lisa	Deep Saline Aquifer	Offshore	29	0.5
Thorning	Deep Saline Aquifer	Onshore	74	0.3

Figure 3-3 Geological storage sites

To complete the integration of the captured emissions in a CCUS network, geological storage is also required for the selected project. The project identified storage sites within the Danish region (onshore and offshore), for which the proposed PCI pipeline would take a key role in supporting the CO₂ supply. These are identified in Table 3-4 and Figure 3-3. The

theoretical numbers supplied by Table 3-4 must be subject to further validation during exploration and appraisal phases.

3.1.2 Contribution to Sustainability

Environmental Sustainability: The project contributes to the capture and transportation of CO₂ emissions, thus reducing the carbon footprint of industrial processes. By facilitating the industrial transition towards low-carbon solutions, it supports the EU's climate goals and helps mitigate climate change.

CO₂ Emissions Reduction Impact: The pipeline project is estimated to result in a substantial reduction of CO₂ emissions by providing a reliable and crucial infrastructure for the transportation of captured CO₂.

Table 3-5 National and international sustainability targets

Phase 1, total transported CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Phase 2, total transported CO ₂ (Mt/y)	German capture target, [6] (Mt/y)	Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS), [7] – 2040 target (Mt/y)	Contribution to ICMS 2040 goals, Phase 2
4.0	7.4	34 to 73	280	2.7%

Efforts to promote sustainability in the region include implementing best practices in pipeline construction and operation to minimise environmental impact.

Environmental impact assessments must be conducted to evaluate potential impacts on natural resources, including land use, water quality, and biodiversity. Mitigation measures must be implemented to minimise adverse effects on the environment.

3.1.3 Cross-border Impact

As a cross-border project between Germany and Denmark, the export pipeline enhances cooperation and connectivity between the two countries' energy systems. It promotes cross-border trade and collaboration in the field of CCUS, contributing to regional integration and resilience. Both Germany and Denmark are contracting parties to the 1996 London Protocol. The Protocol mandates the conclusion of an arrangement or agreement between the exporting and importing countries when the CO₂ is transported across borders for the purpose of offshore storage. Thus, if the offshore storage sites are used, a London Protocol arrangement or agreement between Germany and Denmark will be needed to facilitate for such commercial projects. A further description of the London Protocol was provided in Deliverable D2.3 [8]. The arrangement or agreement may address the transfer of responsibility for any leakage or other incidents between Germany and Denmark along the value chain, and to which country obligations to report and monitor CO₂ leakages apply in accordance with EU legislation (e.g., the EU ETS and the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation – MRR) and international law. Regardless, as stipulated in Article 49 MRR, the ETS responsibility will follow the value chain, and the commercial parties may dictate the

points of transfer for e.g. responsibility in a commercial contract; provided it does not deviate from Article 49 or other relevant EU legislation.

3.2 Pipeline infrastructure to Gdańsk CO₂ terminal

Project Name: Pipelines to the Port of Gdańsk

Location: Northern Poland, South-Eastern Lithuania (and Northern Czechia railway transport) to Port of Gdańsk

Involved Member States: Poland, Lithuania, Czechia (storage sites under North Sea in DK, NO, NL and UK)

Capacity: 9 Mt/y in 2030-2040

Pipelines: 932 km

Figure 3-4 Proposed pipeline infrastructure for the selected PCI.

The following PCI proposes an extension to the planned ECO2CEE PCI, referred in Table 2-1 and led by Orlen S.A., [9]. The ECO2CEE PCI includes multi-modal export/import CO₂ Terminal in Poland, in Port of Gdańsk (Figure 3-4). In the present report, a CO₂ pipeline transport infrastructure is proposed from Northern Poland and South-East Lithuania to the Port of Gdansk. Potential inclusion of CO₂ emissions from Czechia transported by railway can be considered.

The CO₂ terminal shall be commissioned by 2027. In an initial stage, ECO2CEE proposes to transport up to 3 Mt/y via rail from the Orlen refineries in Płock, Poland. Potentially, the Mazeikai/Telšiai, in Lithuania, and the LaFarge-Holcim cement plant Kujawy in Piechcin-Bielawy, Poland will also export their captured emissions using a railway system. The first stage ECO2CEE emitters are presented in blue in Figure 3-4.

The current report focuses on the following stage of the project, aiming to achieve a CO₂ capacity of 9 Mt/y. A CO₂ pipeline network is proposed, represented in red in Figure 3-4, supplementing and, likely, gradually replacing transport via rail contracted in the first stage. We also propose to transport the CO₂ captured emissions of industrial installations in Czechia via rail, at this stage. The present report proposes additional detailing and description of a concept for the second stage of the ECO2CEE existing PCI, leading to a potential extension of the terminal capacities in Gdąnsk.

3.2.1 Contribution to Market Integration

The PCI project integrates various industries from the participating countries, including Cement, Waste to Energy, Paper and Pulp, Refineries, Chemical and Power Plants, to a common CCUS network. Four Orlen Refineries in Poland, Lithuania, and Czechia and two LOTOS Refineries in Poland aggregate the largest share of CO₂ emissions – 6.7 Mt/y. Two Paper and Pulp installations in Poland translate approximately into 4.7 Mt/y. The power sector includes six plants in Poland and Lithuania of various capacities, totalling 3.0 Mt/y. There are also three Waste-to-Energy plants in Lithuania and one in Poland (total emissions 0.6 Mt/y). Chemical and Cement plants also take a key role in the CO₂ toll to be captured. Because of the planned capacity of CO₂ terminal in Gdąnsk, about 56% of these emissions is proposed for a CCUS value chain. Capturing biogenic CO₂ has higher priority than fossil CO₂.

Table 3-6 lists the industries benefitting from the integrated CO₂ market. The proposed captured emissions are within the capacity of Port of Gdąnsk terminal (lower than 9 Mt/y). In case higher CO₂ capture efficiency or added Polish and Czech emitters, the terminal must be significantly upscaled.

Table 3-6 Emission sources proposed by CCUS ZEN for the second stage of Gdąnsk PCI (Poland, Lithuania, and Czechia). Emission sources selected by Orlen for the first ECO2CEE stage are marked with an asterisk (*)

No.	Facility Name	Company Name	City	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported in 2021 (Total) (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Biomass and WtE CO ₂ (Mt/y)
1*	LAFARGE CEMENT S.A. Oddział w Bielawach	LAFARGE CEMENT SPÓŁKA AKCYJNA	Piechcin-Bielawy	Cement	1.27	1.15	0.12

No.	Facility Name	Company Name	City	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported in 2021 (Total) (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Biomass and WtE CO ₂ (Mt/y)
	(Lafarge Kujawy)						
2*	Rafineria (Orlen Płock)	Polski Koncern Naftowy ORLEN S.A.	Płock	Refineries	2.56	2.56	0
3	Bydgoszcz WtE (Bydgoszcz WtE)	MKUO ProNatura Sp. z o.o.	Bydgoszcz	WtE	0.16		0.16
4	Mondi Świecie Spółka Akcyjna (Mondi Świecie)	Mondi Świecie Spółka Akcyjna	Świecie	Paper and pulp	3.97	0.71	3.9
5	ELEKTROCIEP ŁOWNIA (Opec-Ineko Grudziądz)	OPEC-INEKO Sp. z o.o.	Grudziądz	Power - CHP	0.15	0.15	0
6	Produkcja papieru i tektury (IP Kwidzyn)	International Paper - Kwidzyn sp. z o.o.	Kwidzyn	Paper and pulp	0.69	0.69	0
7	ELEKTROCIEP ŁOWNIA ELBLĄG (Energa Elbląg)	ENERGA Kogeneracja	Elbląg	Power - CHP	0.22	0.17	0.06
8	INSTALACJE RAFINERYJNE (Lotos Gdańsk)	GRUPA LOTOS S.A.	Gdańsk	Refineries	1.52	1.52	0
9	LOTOS ASFALT Sp. z o.o. Zakład Produkcyjny Gdańsk (Lotos Asphalt Gdańsk)	LOTOS ASFALT sp. z o.o.	Gdańsk	Refineries	0.2	0.2	0
10	ODDZIAŁ ELEKTROCIEP ŁOWNIA GDAŃSKA (PGE Gdańsk)	PGE Energia Ciepła S.A.	Gdańsk	Power - CHP	1.34	1.34	0.005

No.	Facility Name	Company Name	City	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported in 2021 (Total) (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Biomass and WtE CO ₂ (Mt/y)
11	ODDZIAŁ ELEKTROCIĘP ŁOWNIA GDYŃSKA (PGE Gdynia)	PGE Energia Ciepła S.A.	Gdynia	Power - CHP	0.67	0.67	0.001
TOTAL FROM POLAND					12.75	8.51	4.25
1*	Orlen Lietuva (Orlen Lietuva Telšiai)	Ab "Orlen Lietuva"	Telšiai	Refineries	1.5	1.5	0
2	Achema (Achema)	Ab "Achema"	Kaunas	Chemical	2.21	2.21	0
3	Kaunas WtEP (Fortum Kaunas WtE)	Fortum (Gren) +Ignitis	Kaunas	WtE	0.2	0	0.2
4	Lietuvos Energijos Gamyba, PP (LEG Vilnius)	Ab "Lietuvos Energijos Gamyba"	Vilnius	Power	0.3	0.3	0
5	Vilniaus Šilumos Tinklai PP N2 (VST Vilnius N2)	Ab "Vilniaus Šilumos Tinklai"	Vilnius	Power	0.29	0.29	0
6	Vilnius WtEP (Fortum Vilnius WtE)	Fortum (Gren)+Ignitis	Vilnius	WtE	0.17	0	0.17
7	UAB Kauno WtEP (UAB Kauno WtE)	UAB Kauno koge-neracine jėgainė	Vilnius	WtE	0.11	0	0.11
TOTAL FROM LITHUANIA					4.79	4.31	0.48
1	ORLEN UNIPETROL RPA, s.r.o. - RAFINÉRIE, Kralupy (Orlen Unipetrol Kralupy)	ORLEN UNIPETROL RPA, s.r.o.	Kralupy nad Vltavou	Refineries	0.52	0.52	0

No.	Facility Name	Company Name	City	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported in 2021 (Total) (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ (Mt/y)	Biomass and WtE CO ₂ (Mt/y)
2	ORLEN UNIPETROL RPA, s.r.o. - RAFINÉRIE, Litvínov (Orlen Unipetrol Litvinov)	ORLEN UNIPETROL RPA, s.r.o.	Litvínov – Záluží	Refineries	0.41	0.41	0
TOTAL FROM CZECHIA					0.92	0.92	0

While Table 3-6 presents the emitted CO₂ per facility in 2021, Table 3-7 calculates the distribution of it to CCU (utilisation) or CCS value chains. It is also understood that not all the emitted CO₂ will be captured due to varied reasons, from capture efficiency to business cases that will rely in other alternatives for decarbonisation rather than CCUS.

Table 3-7: Captured CO₂ for storage and utilisation

	CO ₂ Reported (Total)	Fossil CO ₂	Biomass and WtE CO ₂
TOTAL emissions (Mt/y)	18.46	13.74	4.73
Captured CO₂, percentage from emitted	-	44%	90%
Captured CO₂ (Mt/y)	10.3	6.04	4.26
For utilisation, percentage from captured	-	-	30%
For utilisation (Mt/y)	1.28	0	1.28
For geological storage (Mt/y)	9.02	6.04	2.98

Out of a potential of 18.5 Mt/y CO₂ emissions, a fraction of that is estimated to be captured. The captured CO₂ is distributed as 1.3 Mt/y for utilisation and 9 Mt/y for storage. While CO₂ for storage is sent for export in the Port of Gdansk, CO₂ for utilisation can be also sent to large volume hubs or to smaller scale individual facilities.

The market integration is secured by a transportation network. ECO2CEE stage one assumes a railway infrastructure. The proposed PCI suggests a gradual transition to a pipeline network from 2030 to 2040. The stage 1 railway network is estimated at 1233 km

length. In stage two, it is reduced to 962 km, supported by a pipeline infrastructure totalling 932 km of length.

Table 3-8: Proposed transport options to Gdansk Port (Poland, Lithuania, and Czechia). The first stage transport by railway proposed by Orlen is marked by an asterisk (*)

From – to	From – to	From – to	From – to	From – to	Total
Railway					
Orlen Czechia – Gdańsk 962 km	Lafarge Kujawy – Gdańsk* 226 km	Płock – Gdańsk* 259 km	Orlen Lietuva – Gdańsk* 748 km	-	2195 km
Pipeline					
Lafarge Kujawy – IP Kwidzyn 123 km	Płock – IP Kwidzyn 138 km	IP Kwidzyn – Gdańsk 78 km	Vilnius-Kaunas – Gdańsk 558 km	Achema – Kaunas 35 km	932 km

The proposed pipeline network in Poland and Lithuania could encourage the construction of a common cross-border regulatory framework for the carbon market. Such network could eventually be extended to taking the role of a CO₂ backbone supporting alternative transportation chains for the selected countries. This would allow the integration of other initiatives, such as CCS Baltic. Viable extension of such network to Czechia would require construction of a country wide network in Poland.

The proposed project overlaps with the CCS Baltic PCI, as some of the same emitters may be applicable to both projects. The CCS Baltic PCI proposes a CO₂ terminal in the Klaipeda port, closer to the Lithuanian emitters. This can be seen as an opportunity for extending the CCUS network to higher volumes of CO₂ from other regions.

3.2.2 Contribution to Sustainability

The project contributes to environmental sustainability by enabling the capture and transportation of a significant part of CO₂ emissions of the region (particularly of northern Poland and Lithuania), thus reducing the carbon footprint of industrial processes there.

Current National Energy and Climate Plans of Poland and Lithuania do not include captured CO₂ target values. Presently large ETS installations emit 190 Mt CO₂ in Poland and 5 Mt CO₂ in Lithuania. In the case of Czechia there are estimates (modelling scenarios) of CO₂ to be captured and stored/used starting from year 2035 (1.0-2.4 Mt/y) till 2050 (3.5-7.8 Mt/y); for comparison, the estimated emissions of ETS installations in Czechia in 2035 are 48-50 Mt CO₂ (now 57 Mt). A more ambitious modelling scenario assumes average capture ratio (in

both ETS and bio installations in Czechia) 9 Mt/y in years 2033-2042 and 18 Mt/y in 2043-2050.

3.2.3 Cross-border Impact

Poland, Czechia, and Lithuania are not parties to the London Protocol. Therefore, the Protocol does not require an arrangement or agreement to export the CO₂. However, the proposed storage countries are all parties to the London Protocol, and they may nevertheless require an arrangement or agreement as part of their state practise. It may also be recommended to enter into such an arrangement or agreement regardless of the London Protocol, with the London Protocol requirements forming a backdrop as a best practise for cross-border CCS value chains. As explained in the Germany-Denmark PCI scenario above, also here may the arrangement or agreement address liability and the States' monitoring and reporting responsibility. Otherwise, the transfer points may be stipulated by the commercial parties in their agreements, provided this is aligned with Article 49 of the MRR and other applicable EU legislation.

In case of changes in Helsinki convention, if CO₂ storage is permitted in the Baltic Sea, CO₂ could be transported from Gdansk to the structures and depleted HC fields in the Polish part of the Baltic Sea. This would be economically positive, comparing to the transportation of CO₂ to the North Sea structures which are under development now.

3.3 Cross-border Pipeline and harbour Infrastructure: Southern Italy-Greece

The case presented in this section is based in the southern part of Italy, with large emission sources from Italy, in the Tarranto, Brindisi and Priolo Garallo emission cluster hubs, as presented in [2]. In addition, we have included two extra emitter hubs: Messina and Cantanzaro (Figure 3-5) that are situated close to existing national gas systems namely (Figure 3-6).

In addition to the intra Italian emitters, we foresee cross-border infrastructure such as shipping CO₂ transport from the Athens emitter cluster in Greece, and other countries such as France. For Greece, the CCUS ZEN project has included the most likely emitters only to support a CCUS network. Athens is considered a key emitter hub.

The new infrastructure is defined below:

- 1) Pipeline westward from CO₂ emitters in Priolo Gargallo, Messina, Cantanzaro to Bradanica, and pipeline eastward from CO₂ emitters in Taranto and Brindisi. For the pipeline infrastructure, two main options are possible:
 - a. Retrofit of existing gas pipeline.
 - b. New pipeline installation in the existing pipe corridor.

For alternative a), reuse of the pipeline depends on the conditions of the pipeline, the material, and the design pressure of the pipeline. For alternative b), the new main pipeline should have an approximate diameter of 12", to transport at least 3 Mt/y in dense phase (high pressure). Smaller pipelines are also required to link emitters within the clusters. The diameter of the pipelines must be defined according to the

design pressure and volumes to be transported. CO₂ transported in gas phase requires a larger diameter. The pipeline is relatively long and may need booster stations to maintain the pressure level.

2) A CCS harbour infrastructure should be established at Brindisi harbour.

Figure 3-5 Map of Proposed PCI Infrastructure in the Italian region. The proposed PCI is highlighted in red and orange. We propose to use the existing national gas pipeline corridor for CO₂ transport from Priolo Gargallo, Taranto and Brindisi Emission Hubs, and shipping transport from Greece to the harbour at Brindisi.

Project Name: New pipeline in Southern Italy, and new CCS harbour at Brindisi

Location: Pipeline from Sicilia to Brindisi, and ship transport from Athen to Brindisi

Involved Member States: Italy and Greece (possibly also France)

Capacity: 19.3 Mt/y in CO₂ emission. Transport capacity is 3.0 Mt/y by pipeline.

Length: 50-513 km

This pipelines and CO₂ harbour infrastructures are proposed as a PCI located in Southern Italy and Greece. It aims to capture, transport and store approximately 3 million tons of CO₂ emitted per year, in an onshore storage site named Brandanica [2]. This is facilitated by a CO₂ pipeline transport infrastructure from Sicily and eastward from Brindisi. We foresee that a harbour CCS infrastructure must be established at Brindisi.

Figure 3-6 Map of existing national gas pipeline network marked. From www.iea.org.

One of the challenges for storage in the Mediterranean region, is the risk of earthquakes that may affect the storage site. The Mediterranean region is a seismic active area, with regional variations in the risk of earthquakes (see Figure 3-7Left). Seismic hazard maps from Italy, shows minimal risk in the southern part of Italy. Also, historical earthquake maps from 1900-2017 show few or no earthquakes in the area with planned storage site (Figure 3-7b). On the other hand, natural gas storage sites are situated close to the planned CO₂ storage site. We know, from other areas with risk of earthquakes like Japan, that CO₂ storage can be managed also with moderate risk for earthquakes. Another challenge that should be checked with local authorities are Natura 2000 areas, to which infrastructure construction impacts should be avoided or mitigated.

Figure 3-7 Left: Seismic hazard map of Italy showing the probability of seismic activity. At the Bradanica site the risk is low. Right: Map of earthquakes in Italy from 1900-2017. Some smaller earthquakes are reported northwest of the Bradanica storage site. From Wikipedia/List of earthquakes in Italy.

Table 3-9 shows an overview of the CCS value chain for the Southern Italy. The data from the emission clusters are collected from Endrava dataset [2], with updates from Messina and Cantanzaro emitter cluster (see Table 3-10).

Table 3-11 gives an overview of the emitter cluster close to Athens, situated at the seaside. This CO₂ industry cluster emits around 9.4 million tons CO₂ per year.

Table 3-9 Summary table for value chain for Southern Italy. The annual emission cluster numbers are based on data from Endrava for 2021.

Value chain	Emission cluster(s)	Annual CO ₂ emissions (Mt/y)	Storage site(s)	Capacity (Mt)	Distance along pipeline gate to onshore storage site (km)	Comment
Southern Italy	Brindisi	6.9	Onshore Bradanica S_IT8	344-1376	110	-
	Taranto	12.4			50	5 km to existing pipeline gate
	Cantanzaro	1.3			181	38.2 km distance to existing pipeline gate
	Messina	3.8			312	-
	Priolo Garallo	7.2			403	73.1 km distance to existing pipeline gate
	TOTAL	31.7			513	116 km pipeline to connect to main pipeline gate

Table 3-10 Point sources included from Southern Italy, data from Endrava database, from year 2021.

Emitter ID	Facility Name	Company Name	State	Industry Sector	Emission Trend	CO ₂ Emissions (Mt/y)
E_IT_10	Raffineria Di Milazzo S.C.P.A.	Raffineria Di Milazzo S.C.P.A.	Messina	Refineries	falling	1.9
E_IT_21	A2A Energiefuture S.P.A.	A2A Energiefuture S.P.A.	Messina	Power	growing	1.3

Emitter ID	Facility Name	Company Name	State	Industry Sector	Emission Trend	CO ₂ Emissions (Mt/y)
E_IT_66	Termica Milazzo S.R.L.	Termica Milazzo S.R.L.	Messina	Power	growing	0.6
Total Messina cluster						3.8

Table 3-11 Overview of emitters close to Athens, Greece. Data from Endrava, 2021.

Emitter ID	Facility Name	Company Name	State	Industry Sector	Emission Trend	CO ₂ Emissions (Mt/y)
E_GR_4	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Attiki	Refineries	growing	1.9
E_GR_5	Titan Cement S.A. -Kamari Plant	Titan Sement S.A.	Attiki	Cement	falling	1.5
E_GR_6	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Attiki	Refineries	growing	1.5
E_GR_29	Sanitary Landfill	Edsna	Attiki	Other	falling	0.2
E_GR_31	Halyps Building Materials S.A.	Heidelberg Cement Group	Attiki	Cement	falling	0.2
E_GR_3	Motor Oil (Hellas)	Motor Oil	Peloponnies	Refineries	growing	2.1
E_GR_24	Korinthos Power S.A	Korinthos Power S.A	Peloponnies	Power	falling	0.6
E_GR_7	Ppc S.A. Ses Kerateas-Layrioy	Ppc S.A. Ses Kerateas-Layrioy	Attiki	Power	growing	1.4
Total Athen Cluster						9.4

Thus, making some assumptions, based on the IEA (2020) report [10] and own work, we assume that not all CO₂ emitted will be stored in the underground. We assume that the captured CO₂ is defined as a percentage per industry sector. We have used the same cut off, with the same reasoning as described more in detail in [3], for the Mediterranean value chain. A summary of the assumptions taken are presented in Table 3-12.

Table 3-13 and Table 3-14 show the summary emissions for the different clusters in Southern Italy and Greece, respectively. Even with a large cut off, for instance, for the iron & steel industry and power, there are still large emissions, specially from southern Italy, but also from the Athens emission hub.

Table 3-12 Summary of CO₂ emitter sector, and CCUS contribution used in the calculations.

Type of industry	CCUS contribution in %	Source	Comments
Chemicals	35	IEA (2020) report [10]	Several other means such as electrification, process efficiency, fuel change exists. We will use values from IEA.
Iron & steel	25	IEA (2020) report [10]	The industry is looking at several other decarbonisation pathways and changes in their processes
Refineries	50	Assumption	Other means such as electrification, process efficiency, fuel charge exists. However, refineries must also use their by-product as fuel so there are more non-reducible emissions. Hence, an average value is proposed.
Power	50	Assumption	Average value taken with the assumption that some of the power plant will convert to biogenic fuel
Cement/Lime	65	IEA (2020) report [10]	Process emissions are still to be managed
Hydrogen	85	Assumption	Less other decarbonisation options for existing installations exists, unless changing the whole plant to Green H ₂ , therefor a high percentage is proposed.

Table 3-13 Overall summary for Italy, using a percentage reduction to obtain the captured CO₂ per industry sector, as per Table 3-12.

Cluster Name	Total CO ₂ Emissions (Mt/y)	Number Of Emitters	CO ₂ Captured Emissions (Mt/y)
Taranto cluster	12.4	7	5.0
Brindisi cluster	6.9	4	3.4
Priolo Garallo cluster	7.2	9	3.5
Messina cluster	3.8	3	1.9
Catanzaro	1.3	1	0.7
Total	31.7	24	14.5

Table 3-14 Overall summary for Greece, using a percentage reduction to obtain the captured CO₂ per industry sector, as per Table 3-12.

Cluster Name	Total CO ₂ Emissions (Mt/y)	Number Of Emitters	CO ₂ Captured Emissions (Mt/y)
Athens cluster	5.3	5	2.8
Agioi Theodoroi cluster	2.8	2	1.4
Lavrion	1.4	1	0.7
Total	9.4	8	4.8

3.3.1 Contribution to Market Integration

We foresee that the suggested PCI between Greece and Italy, will contribute to market integration between the two countries. In addition, we see that by establishing a CCS harbour infrastructure at Brindisi, CO₂ transported from other neighbouring countries like south-eastern part of France would be probable and help the integration of fluid transactions across borders. We aim to use the existing natural pipeline corridors, and to increase the CO₂ pipeline capacity for use within EU.

This PCI aligns with the EU CCUS objectives, since the projects open a cross-border transport path, located in a new geographically area which, until now, has only one PCI developed in the same theme. This is the offshore underground storage in Prinos, Greece. Since the project of common interest that we suggest is close to many large emitter clusters situated in the southern Italy (Table 3-13), we do not see any real competition between both projects. The demand for storage sites is large, even with using conservative estimates assuming CCUS contributions between 25% to 65 % dependent on the industry sector. Below, a list of the different industry emitters in southern Italy (Table 3-15), that would benefit directly of such CCUS value chain is presented. These are mapped in Figure 3-5 and the corresponding list for Greece is shown in Table 3-11.

Table 3-15 Overview of industries in the different clusters in southern Italy.

Cluster Name	Emitter ID	Company Name	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported (Mt/y)	Emission Trend
Taranto cluster	E_IT_2	ArcelorMittal Italia	Iron & Steel	5.2	falling
Taranto cluster	E_IT_3	Taranto Energia S.R.L. In Amministrazione Straordinaria	Power	4.4	growing
Taranto cluster	E_IT_25	Eni S.P.A.	Refineries	1.1	growing

Cluster Name	Emitter ID	Company Name	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported (Mt/y)	Emission Trend
Taranto cluster	E_IT_52	Eni S.P.A.	Refineries	0.7	falling
Taranto cluster	E_IT_75	Italcementi Spa	Cement	0.5	growing
Taranto cluster	E_IT_103	Eni S.P.A.	Refineries	0.3	growing
Taranto cluster	E_IT_135	Tecnoparco Valbasento S.P.A.	Power	0.2	growing
Brindisi cluster	E_IT_5	Enel Produziane S.P.A.	Power	3.9	Falling
Brindisi cluster	E_IT_6	Enipower S.P.A.	Power	2.6	growing
Brindisi cluster	E_IT_92	Versalis S.P.A.	Chemicals (other)	0.4	Falling
Brindisi cluster	E_IT_227	Firenze Fpso	Other	0.04	Falling
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_8	Esso Italiana S.R.L.	Refineries	2.0	growing
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_15	Isab S.R.L	Refineries	1.7	falling
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_33	Erg Power S.R.L.	Power	0.9	falling
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_44	Versalis S.P.A.	Chemicals (other)	0.8	growing
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_72	Buzzi Unicem Spa	Cement	0.5	growing
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_73	Enel Produzione S.P.A.	Power	0.5	growing
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_80	Sasol Italy S.P.A.	Chemicals (other)	0.5	growing
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_116	Isab S.R.L	Power	0.2	falling
Priolo Garallo cluster	E_IT_173	Air Liquide Italia Produzione S.R.L.	Hydrogen	0.1	falling
Messina cluster	E_IT_10	Raffineria Di Milazzo S.C.P.A.	Refineries	1.9	falling
Messina cluster	E_IT_21	A2A Energiefuture S.P.A.	Power	1.3	growing

Cluster Name	Emitter ID	Company Name	Industry Sector	CO ₂ Reported (Mt/y)	Emission Trend
Messina cluster	E_IT_66	Termica Milazzo S.R.L.	Power	0.6	growing
Catanzaro	E_IT_22	Edison S.P.A.	Power	1.3	falling

3.3.2 Contribution to Sustainability

Table 3-13 and Table 3-14 shows that even by assuming industrial sector reduction in the CO₂ that will be stored, there will be up to 19.3 Mt/y available for underground storage. Storing part of this CO₂ volumes, will have a significantly contribution to the sustainability of the EU's energy systems. However, the amount stored, will also be dependent on the storage capacity. For the "Bradonica" storage site, we do not have access to dynamic reservoir simulations. A static storage capacity between 344 Mt, using a conservative storage efficiency of 1%, and 1376 million tonnes was estimated using a storage efficiency of 4%, assuming a reservoir porosity of 25% [11]. Often, a storage efficiency of 2% is assumed, that will correspond to 688 Mt storage capacity. If we assume that we have two injection wells, injecting 3 million tonnes per well per year, the site should be able to store 180 Mt over 30 years. Another possibility is to use depleted hydrocarbon fields also located in the Basilicata region, such as "Cugno le Machine" (area 48 km²), with two different reservoir units: "Grotole" and "Ferrandina" or the abandoned field "Serra Pizzuta" [12].

A third options, would be to explore offshore storage units, offshore Sicily as presented in [12].

3.3.3 Cross-border Impact

The project will have a significant impact on the CCUS value chain for Italy and Greece, since it will open short transportation routes using existing onshore natural pipeline corridors. As Figure 3-5 shows, there are several large CO₂ emitter hubs geographically situated close to the pipeline corridor. For Greece, and specially the Athens emitters hub, the transport route to Brindisi is geographically close. It can also be an option, to ship CO₂ from southern France.

Italy and France are both contracting parties to the London Protocol, while Greece is not. France will need to conclude an arrangement or agreement with Italy in line with the London Protocol. Greece may not need to conclude such an arrangement or agreement as a non-Contracting Party, but it is recommended, and Italy may nevertheless require it. As all countries are EU member states, the EU ETS and MRR, and the general environmental liability regime will also apply here. The arrangement or agreement may, or may not, contain criteria relating to e.g. responsibility, reporting and monitoring of leakages, potentially providing a basis for commercial agreements.

3.4 Additional proposed PCI

This section analyses an additional PCI that was studied in various stages of the CCUS ZEN project and is also important to mention.

3.4.1 Harbour and offshore pipeline infrastructure in Tarragona

Project Name: Tarragona hub

Location: Tarragona (Spain)

Involved Member States: Spain, France

Capacity: 9.8 Mt/y

Length: 48.1 km

Figure 3-8 CCUS value chain for Western Mediterranean – In dashed red is the proposed PCI in Tarragona. Total captured emissions for the 3 clusters amount to 9.77 Mt/y.

The proposed PCI in Tarragona consists of common infrastructures to gather and transport the emissions from industrial clusters in Spain and France to an offshore storage site. These infrastructures are part of the CCUS value chain proposed for western Mediterranean region (Figure 3-8). Emissions originate from three industrial clusters: Tarragona, Barcelona, and Fos-Marseille. CO₂ is transported to a gathering hub at the Tarragona harbour. From there, carbon dioxide is transported to a storage site offshore via pipeline. The infrastructures

proposed for PCI are the infrastructures common to the three clusters, i.e. the gathering hub in Tarragona and the offshore pipeline to storage.

Table 3-16 Quantities of CO₂ captured by cluster

Country	Cluster	Number of emitters	CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)
Spain	Tarragona Cluster	5	1.98
	Barcelona Cluster	9	2.25
France	Fos-Marseille Cluster	18	5.54
Total		32	9.77

Detailed information about the gathering hub in Tarragona and the offshore pipeline are provided in D3.1 of the CCUS ZEN project [3], where technical description of the infrastructures is available. The offshore pipeline would transport up to 9.77 Mt/y of CO₂ to the storage site. This would result, for 20 years operations project, in a total 190 Mt of stored CO₂.

The Tarragona PCI would enable the export and the storage of CO₂ emissions from the French industrial clusters of Fos-Marseille in Spain, in addition to the emissions from the local clusters (Tarragona, Barcelona). In the Fos cluster, the potential for CO₂ capture is high, while the local storage potential is low. Exporting CO₂ by ship is already considered. The CALLISTO PCI plans harbour infrastructures to gather and liquefy CO₂ for shipping to Ravenna (Italy). The Tarragona project would represent an additional storage alternative for the Fos region, where the demand for capture is high. Moreover, transporting CO₂ from the Rhone valley to Fos is under consideration, which would increase the amount of CO₂ to be shipped to storage.

4 Stakeholder Analysis for the Proposed PCI

Effective implementation of PCI as large infrastructure projects requires the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders, necessitating coordination and collaboration across various sectors to ensure project success. In cross-country projects, the coordination and collaboration of diverse stakeholders is crucial to navigate regulatory differences and ensure smooth project execution.

Table 4-1 lists various general stakeholders applicable for the multiple countries of each project, categorising them into regulatory authorities, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), financial institutions, and project developers and partners. The table outlines each stakeholder's responsibilities and actions, listing their roles in facilitating the CCUS infrastructure.

In the following subsections, detailed information can be found for each country regarding expected stakeholder involvement in the proposed PCI.

Table 4-1 List of stakeholders

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Regulatory authorities		
Municipalities	<p>Municipality plan.</p> <p>Local plan.</p> <p>Land zone permit.</p> <p>Protected nature according to national law.</p> <p>Polluted soil and water resources.</p> <p>Protected stone- and earth dikes.</p> <p>Nature protection zones/lines</p>	<p>In the municipalities where either compressor stations or other buildings are to be established, the responsible planning authority is the respective municipality. They are also responsible for a wide range of other environmental factors that may be affected by the project.</p>
Agency for Culture and Palaces	Cultural heritage both sites and areas.	Ensures that the provisions of the Museum Act are complied with in connection with construction work near protected ancient monuments.
Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)		
Bellona	The organisation strives to identify and implement sustainable solutions to the world's most pressing environmental issues. Its main goals are to combat the climate crisis, environmental degradation, pollution-induced hazards to human health, and the ecological consequences of economic development strategies.	<p>Integrate scientific systems-thinking and foresight in policymaking.</p> <p>Accelerate credible climate solution and the availability of decarbonisation infrastructure.</p> <p>Ensure transparency and accountability through awareness-raising and public participation</p>
Concito	Facilitates knowledge about subjects to the green transition and thereby to accelerates it.	<p>Conduct pertinent analyses and generate novel insights.</p> <p>Facilitate the connection between scientific findings and policymaking.</p> <p>Assist decision-makers in adopting and implementing practical solutions.</p> <p>Provide a neutral and central platform for fostering dialogue on the green transition.</p>
The Council for Green Transition	An organisation working to promote the green transition by developing and sharing knowledge about new green solutions that influence decision-makers, companies, and citizens to move in a green direction	Their visions entail a green and sustainable society, a carbon-neutral Denmark, and ensuring well-thought-out holistic solutions. These visions are to be created in collaboration with others, as they cannot be achieved alone.

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Financial Institutions		
INNO-CCUS	In 2020, it was decided to establish four green research missions under the Innovation Fund, focusing on either capture and storage or utilisation of CO ₂ .	INNO-CCUS is a broad research collaboration involving 54 different actors from both the public and private sectors, including universities, research institutions, and companies. In 2022, the partnership awarded the first round of project grants.
EU Innovation Fund	The EU's Innovation Fund aims to support groundbreaking technologies and comprehensive projects in Europe that have the potential to achieve significant CO ₂ reductions. Through the EU's Innovation Fund, support can be sought for a range of initiatives, including CCS projects.	The EU's Innovation Fund operates with two distinct pools: one for larger projects with a total budget exceeding €7.5 million, and another for smaller projects with a total budget below €7.5 million.
Connecting Europe Facility, Energy	Among other funding opportunities within the EU, it is also possible to apply for support for CCS projects involving at least two EU member states.	To obtain support through the so-called Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), it is a requirement that the project be listed on the EU's list of projects with PCI status.
Project developers and partners		
Not listed emitters, T&S operators or CCU industry	To create an integrated market for the development of CCUS networks.	Engage in capture, transport, utilisation, and storage of CO ₂ , with specific projects.
CO ₂ Hub Europe	A coalition of the largest stakeholders within CCS in Denmark, the coalition consists of both developers and researchers.	The objective is to contribute to developing Denmark's potential to become Europe's central CO ₂ hub. This is done, among other things, through an analysis project aimed at elucidating the regulation, financing, and risk allocation between private actors and the state in connection with CCS.
Consultancy, research organisations and EPC contractors	Support the development and operationalisation of CCUS networks	Through design, manufacturing, installation and commissioning services, consultancy, research centres and EPC contractors are crucial to operationalise CCUS networks. Additionally, they can perform business-oriented research and create roadmaps for the implementation of CCUS solutions.

4.1 Denmark

In Germany to Denmark pipeline Link, the pipeline infrastructure of the proposed PCI (Jutland network) will run onshore the entire stretch between Denmark and Germany. In connection hereby, there are several stakeholders who will have an influence on the project. This covers both regulatory authorities and permitting, developers as well as interests from different NGO's.

The regulatory aspects and permitting covers nature considerations, such as Natura 2000 and Annex IV species, and the water framework directive, cultural heritage, safety issues,

and citizen's health. The regulatory aspect also covers municipal and local planning as a fundament to realise the project.

Several NGOs work positively to promote the development of CCUS and the pipeline infrastructure and make the challenges or possibilities that exist visible. This is to illuminate and present it to the decision makers or authorities. To promote the development of CCUS and pipeline infrastructure, there are several opportunities for financial support, which are offered by several stakeholders both nationally and in the EU.

The last stakeholder in relation to the implementation of CCUS infrastructure is the project developers and their partners. It is the stakeholders who help ensure the expansion takes place from a commercial perspective. In the following section, the stakeholders are divided into the following groups: Regulatory authorities, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO), Financial Institutions, and Project developers and partners. Their individual role and influence will be described further in the sections below.

Regulatory authorities

This group of stakeholders are the authorities which are the ones that are going to issue the permits and therefore they have a profound influence in the realisation of the project. A CO₂ pipeline infrastructure project is subject to § 15 of the Environmental Assessment Act, as such projects appear in Appendix 1 No. 16 of the Environmental Assessment Act. The purpose of environmental impact assessment is to ensure that an assessment of the effects on the environment is conducted as a basis for the decision to grant or refuse permission for types of installations that may significantly affect the environment. A facility for collection of CO₂ streams where the purpose is geological storage is also covered by Appendix 1 No. 6.9 of the Approval Order. An environmental permit typically contains conditions for the layout and operation of the company, ensuring that the company operates without significant environmental impact on the surroundings. The project therefore also requires an environmental approval according to § 33 of the Environmental Protection Act, to allow the establishment and operation of the facility. The authority for both permissions is the Danish Environmental Protection Agency.

The necessary planning basis must also be secured in the early planning stage in accordance with provisions in the Planning Act. The Act's purpose is to ensure holistic planning that integrates different interests in the use of land, while protecting nature and the environment and creating optimal conditions for sustainable growth and development. In general, the municipalities are the planning authority, but for large infrastructure projects, the Government takes over as the responsible authority.

Permission from the Danish Energy Agency is also required for the establishment and operation of a pipeline facility, cf. § 23u of the Underground Act. According to this, the works conducted along with the establishment must also be approved, cf. § 28 of the Underground Act. § 23t of the Underground Act sets out several provisions for potential users to use a CO₂ pipeline infrastructure

In addition to the above permits, it will be necessary to obtain several smaller permits on an ongoing basis. This could be permits, for example, for handling contaminated soil,

groundwater lowering, under drilling of roads and watercourses. The actual extent can only be fully clarified when a project has reached a higher level of detail.

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

This group of stakeholders all have the common goal of promoting the expansion of initiatives aimed at reducing CO₂ emissions, including new technological forms such as CCUS. They work to create transparency for investors and to translate the latest knowledge into actual climate action. This is done to ensure that Denmark meets its obligations to reduce CO₂ emissions and, in this context, plays a role in developing innovative technologies to accelerate the green transition.

Financial Institutions

Due to the complexity of these types of projects and the overall common goal to reduce the CO₂ emission, there are multiple stakeholders offering financial support in the form of grant schemes. This is also done to promote the expansion process of, among others, CCUS and pipeline infrastructure. The various support options are managed at both national and EU levels.

Project developers and partners

This group of stakeholders is relatively extensive as it consists of actors who face the challenges and seek solutions, encompassing the entire value chain from capturing to transporting and storing CO₂. This means it consist of industries emitting CO₂ who are implementing new CO₂ capture technologies for the purpose of storage. The stakeholders could also be entities that can utilise the captured CO₂, such as Power-to-X technologies. For this value chain to succeed, investment in CO₂ infrastructure is required, and there are several stakeholders along with the proposed PCI (Jutland network) who are interested in ensuring the expansion of this infrastructure to avoid creating a bottleneck in CO₂ transportation.

Additional specific stakeholders are named in Table 4-2.

Table 4-2 List of stakeholders (Denmark)

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Danish Environmental Protection Agency	Environmental Impact Assessment Environmental Approval Protected Forest	Nature protection, including Natura 2000 areas, Annex IV species. Environmental protection.
Danish Energy Agency	Permits regarding the Underground Act.	Is the authority regarding approvals cf. the Danish Underground Act.

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Green Power Denmark	A green industry organisation working to promote the Danish energy sector, whose members consist of a range of stakeholders across the Danish energy sector.	They work to ensure that in Denmark, our ambitions, framework conditions, and research maintain our green leadership position and generate prosperity and jobs and for investors in green energy that require clear and stable investment frameworks to ensure an adequate supply of green energy.
Danish Industry - Energy	Works to put the Danish energy industry on the political agenda, as well as to promote visibility both nationally and internationally.	Acting by: Political advocacy, Consultation and advisory support, Network, Export promotion.
State of Green	Danish organisation working to disseminate Danish solutions for the green transition internationally.	They work to strengthen Danish exports, attract foreign investors, and accelerate the global green transition through events, webinars, publications, and delegation visits.
CCUS-puljen	A market-based, technology-neutral fund aimed at promoting the capture, storage, and utilisation of CO ₂ .	In the first phase, it should contribute to CO ₂ reductions of 0.4 million tons annually from 2025, and in the second phase, it should be 0.9 million tons annually from 2030. The funds would cover costs at all stages of the CCUS value chain, and the support is allocated per ton of reduced CO ₂
NECCS-puljen	The political agreement from December 2021 on the "Sub-agreement on Investments in a Continued Greener Denmark under the Finance Act for 2022" introduces a new fund of 2.5 billion DKK aimed at achieving a reduction of 0.5 million tons annually from 2025 through CO ₂ capture.	The fund has been established with the aim of achieving an additional 0.5 million tons of negative emissions annually from 2025 through CO ₂ capture. Through this fund, support can be provided for negative emissions from CO ₂ capture from biogenic sources and subsequent storage underground.
Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme (EUDP)	A public grant schemes.	The program supports the advancement of innovative technologies, including CCS-related technologies, which can help to fulfil Denmark's energy and climate goals.
Energinet/Gas Storage Denmark	Energinet and their subsidiary, Gas Storage Denmark, have developed and accelerated knowledge for the CCS industry.	They have done this, among other things, through the first pilot project of CO ₂ storage in Denmark onshore, with the intention of contributing knowledge and experience on storing CO ₂ in the Danish subsurface.
Evida	As Denmark's national gas distributor and since the Danish government's proposal is for the expansion of CCS to be based on a market-driven model, where both private and public entities can own and operate CO ₂ transport pipelines.	Since they have many years of experience in operating and establishing pipelines for gas, they believe they have the knowledge and experience to contribute to the establishment of Denmark's CO ₂ infrastructure.

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Nordsøfonden	The Danish state's subsurface company, whose task is to create value by optimising the use of the Danish subsurface in the best viable way.	Nordsøfonden represents the Danish state in all CO ₂ storage licenses with a 20% share. Additionally, depending on the specific project, Nordsøfonden may also become co-owners of relevant infrastructure, transportation, and storage facilities.

4.2 Germany

Regulatory authorities

The laying and operation of a CO₂ pipeline requires a permit in accordance with §4 of the German Carbon Dioxide Storage Act (Kohlendioxid-Speicherungsgesetz, KSpG), [13]. The project is authorised in a planning approval procedure and since an Environmental Impact Assessment is also required for the project, the procedure must be conducted with public participation.

Due to the federal structure in Germany, different authorities are responsible for the authorisation. However, since the planned pipelines are transit pipelines, it needs to be approved according to §133 BBergG (Federal Mining Act) (1) by the responsible state office (§136 BBergG) and (2) by the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, BSH).

For Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania the responsible authority for transit pipelines is the State Office for Mining in Stralsund (Bergamt Stralsund). For the state of Lower Saxony and Schleswig Holstein the State Office for Mining and Energy (Landesamt für Bergbau und Energie, LBEG) in Clausthal-Zellerfeld is the regulatory authority for project approval. Because the pipelines for the Denmark/Germany project are planned onshore in the state of Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and will run offshore through German Territorial Waters as well as the EEZ, three jurisdictions are affected by the project. For all three jurisdictions affected by the project, the State Office for Mining in Stralsund (Bergamt Stralsund) is the superior approval authority for the procedure. When a project includes waters belonging to the EEZ, several federal offices are automatically involved in addition.

For the states of Lower Saxony and Schleswig-Holstein the State Office for Mining and Energy (Landesamt für Bergbau und Energie, LBEG) in Clausthal-Zellerfeld is the superior approval authority. Nevertheless, for both federal states each jurisdiction has separate approval procedures which must be implemented. Depending on the respective jurisdiction, different authorities must be involved in the approval procedures. These authorities will be included over the course of the permitting procedure by the superior approval authority which oversees the overall process.

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

In Germany Non-Governmental-Organisations are more critical of the implementation of CO₂ – pipelines as they see the use as a tool to prolong unsustainable energy sources such as

gas-fired power plants. Especially NGOs like Deutsche Umwelthilfe (DUH) regularly sue the government and companies for environmentally harmful projects. Other NGOs which are politically active are Greenpeace and WWF. The organisations NABU and BUND are also widespread and relevant in Germany, however they rarely intervene politically in planned controversial projects of companies or the government.

Additional specific stakeholders are named in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3: List of stakeholders (Germany)

Name	Responsibility/ Strategies	Action
Federal Environmental Agency (Umweltbundesamt)	Germany's federal environmental protection agency	Primary federal agency mandated to protect the environment and to issue analyses and assessments.
Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe)	Germany's central competence centre on geosciences and use of natural resources.	Responsible for storage site security, assessment of environmental impacts and international norms.
State Office for Mining Stralsund (Bergamt Stralsund)	Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (and its Territorial Waters), Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)	For transit pipelines the Bergamt Stralsund is in charge. For non-transit pipelines smaller than 300 mm (diameter) the affected counties can permit.
State Office for Mining, Energy and Geology (Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geologie, LBEG)	Lower Saxony, parts of Schleswig Holstein	The LBEG in Clausthal-Zellerfeld is the superior approval authority for the permitting procedure in both federal states.
Federation of German Industries (Bundesverband Deutsche Industrie, BDI)	Umbrella organisation of German industry and industry-related service providers	Acting by: Public relations, Representation of the industry interests
German Association for Negative Emissions (Deutscher Verband Negativemissionen)	Umbrella organisation of German CDR players	Acting by: Public relations, Representation of the CDR industry interests
Deutsche Umwelthilfe (DUH) German Environmental Aid	German organisation for environmental protection	Acting by: Public relations, Representation of the public interest, lawsuits against environmentally controversial projects
Greenpeace	Worldwide organisation for environmental protection and peace	Acting by: public relations, organised protests, lawsuits against environmentally controversial projects
WWF	Worldwide organisation for environmental protection	Acting by: public relations, organised protests, lawsuits against environmentally controversial projects

Name	Responsibility/ Strategies	Action
NABU	German organisation for environmental protection and education	Acting by: public relations, organised protests, education programs, mainly locally organised Rarely involved in lawsuits, usually not involved at state level
BUND	German organisation for environmental protection and education	Acting by: public relations, organised protests, education programs, mainly locally organised Rarely involved in lawsuits, usually not involved at state level
RWE	A German multinational energy company, which generates and trades energy in Europe, the US and Asia-Pacific region	RWE has planned CO ₂ pipelines in the past and as a major energy company is constantly working on new solution for energy generation and carbon capture and storage.
Wintershall DEA	A German subsidiary of the big chemical producer BASF. Specialises in production of gas and oil.	With its own subsidiary WIGA Transport Beteiligungs-GmbH & Co KG Wintershall DEA has already built more than 4,000 km of gas pipelines and is willing to reconstruct to be able to transport CO ₂ as well.
OGE	Open Grid Europe (OGE) is an energy company, mainly focused on natural gas and biogas.	OGE is already part of CCS Europe (advocacy and communication body supported by NGOs, developers, etc.) with a pipeline network with a length of about 12,000 kilometres.
Heidelberg Materials	Heidelberg Materials is a German multinational building materials company.	Heidelberg Materials like other Concrete Manufacturers are extremely interested in CCS for neutralising their sector typical high emissions. HM is already receiving funding from European innovation funds for their "GeZero" project.

4.3 Poland

Regulatory authorities

The regulatory authority on CO₂ storage (including licenses, concessions) in Poland is the Ministry of Climate and Environment. We highlight the figures of the Deputy Minister, the Chief Geologist of State, supported by Department of Geology, and the relevant regulations included in geological of mining law and accompanying ordinances. Prospecting of CO₂ storage requires opinion of a local authority. Applying for storage permits agreement with a local authority is required. The regulatory authority on transport of gases is the Energy Regulatory Authority, however regulations and duties specific to carbon dioxide are, at this moment, only vaguely mentioned in the relevant law and the legal framework is not fully completed. The General Directorate for Environmental Protection and its regional branches are responsible for relevant environmental issues pertaining to CO₂ storage and transport.

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

There are international NGOs active in this field in Poland like Bellona Foundation, WiseEuropa and numerous local organisations which engage in the CCUS discussions at various levels.

Financial Institutions

The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management could finance infrastructure and research projects. The National Centre of Research of Development is also capable of funding research activities, but there no programmes or calls dedicated specifically to CCUS at this moment (hence these institutions are not listed among stakeholders in Table 4-4).

Project developers and partners

The PCI ECO2CEE project is led by the Polish fuel company Orlen. Its subsidiaries are Orlen Lietuva in Lithuania and Unipetrol in Czechia. Additional partners and developers could be Holcim (LaFarge) Poland (developer of Kujawy Go4ECOPlanet project intertwined with the PCI), Air Liquide Poland and the Port of Gdańsk Authority. Other additional important stakeholders are presented in Table 4-4.

Additional specific stakeholders are named in Table 4-4.

Table 4-4 List of stakeholders (Poland)

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
(Polish) Ministry of Climate and Environment	Permits according to the Geological and Mining Law	Authority regarding approvals cf. the Polish Geological and Mining Law.
The (Polish) General Directorate for Environmental Protection and its regional branches	Environmental Impact Assessment Environmental Approval of investments	Nature protection, including Natura 2000 areas, protected animal, and plant species. Environmental protection.
WiseEuropa	Polish think-tank undertaking a strategic reflection on European politics, foreign policy, and economy	Engaging citizens, entrepreneurs, experts and policymakers from Poland and other countries in a joint reflection on the EU's and Poland's modernisation agenda as well as the EU's and Poland's role in the world – particularly on RES, transition of the energy sector, decarbonisation, Polish and European energy, and climate policy
Orlen	Polish multinational oil refiner, petrol retailer and natural gas trader headquartered in Płock, Poland is recently focusing on energy	The company objectives include reduction of CO ₂ emissions & emissions intensity in the refinery, petrochemicals, and upstream segments through several actions. One example is the implementation of CCUS technologies, including the development of a CO ₂ terminal in Gdańsk (as a consortium

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
	transition strategies, to become net zero by 2050.	leader; ECO2CEE PCI project) and industrial scale CO ₂ capture units. Because the company upstream assets include hydrocarbon E&P operators, storage in depleted hydrocarbon fields is planned as well.
Holcim (formerly LaFarge) Poland	Holcim in Poland belongs to the Holcim Group, which is the first company in the cement sector in the world to sign the Net-Zero Pledge – to reduce its CO ₂ emissions by at least 20% by 2030 compared to 2018. In Poland, Holcim's ambition is to reduce emission levels by 55% compared to 1990.	Holcim intends to achieve this goal by decarbonising the value chain, i.e. all processes related to the company's operations. Particularly in 2027, the Kujawy Cement Plant will become the first zero-emission cement plant in Poland where a CO ₂ capture facility will make it possible to reduce the carbon footprint of the sintering process of clinker, which is the basic ingredient in cement production.

4.4 Lithuania

Regulatory authorities

Lithuania's energy policy is developed and coordinated by the Ministry of Energy. The development and implementation of Lithuanian climate change mitigation policies is coordinated by the Ministry of the Environment. These two ministries cooperate with the Ministries of Finance, Transport, Economy and Innovation, Education, Science and Sport, Agriculture, Foreign Affairs, Defence of the Country, Culture, Social Security and Labour, Health and Interior, and with the relevant committees of the national parliament, municipalities, the Lithuanian Scientific Council, state research institutions, universities, companies and social partners in the development of energy and climate policies.

A National Climate Change Committee has been established to provide independent scientific advice on development of national climate change management policies. It is composed of 11 representatives from different higher education institutions in the country. Scientists will provide advice on research or funding pathways needed to implement climate change policies to achieve GHG reduction targets, on climate-relevant research, innovation, and draft national climate change management reports [14].

In the Baltic Sea Region, Lithuania was the only country that allowed CO₂ geological storage both onshore and offshore before October 2019. In October 2019, the new government of Lithuania, with a large lobby from an agricultural party, adopted a new Subsurface Law. As a result, the injection and/or storage of carbon dioxide in natural and/or artificial underground cavities and/or aquifers was prohibited. This ban came into force on the 1st of July 2020 [15].

Lithuania has submitted the final version of its NECP–2024 (National Energy and Climate Plan) in October 2024 [14]. The measures to deploy CCUS technologies include:

- Deployment of carbon capture technologies with priority for biogenic carbon capture and atmospheric CO₂, which can then be used to produce synthetic energy products (e-methane and e-methanol), or transfer to permanent storage with negative emissions (2024-2050).

- Establishment of carbon dioxide transport infrastructure. The infrastructure will be dedicated to both the export of fossil CO₂ and the import of biogenic CO₂ that will be used by local actors as feedstock (e.g. to produce synthetic fuels). (2024-2030).
- Establishing a carbon recovery market and developing its potential. Development of standards and market conditions for synthetic products produced using H₂ and CO₂. (2025-2030).
- Establishment of a CO₂ monitoring system.
 - This plan includes some predictive numbers for CO₂ emissions captured (Fossil CO₂: 2.4 Mt/y by 2040 and 1 Mt/y by 2050, biogenic CO₂: 0.2 Mt/y by 2030, 3.5 Mt/y by 2040 and 3.5 Mt by 2050), used, transported and monitored. Geological CO₂ storage in Lithuania is not included. All produced biogenic CO₂ is planned for CO₂ utilisation [14].

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

Bellona Foundation is an active NGO in the Baltic Region and Lithuania. In the CCS4CEE project several NGOs (WiseEuropa, Bellona, etc.) and CIVITTA provided Lithuania with consultancy services.

BASRECCS is Baltic CCS association registered in Finland, and active in the Baltic Sea Region since 2015 [16]. The BASRECCS network of CCS expertise in the Baltic Sea Region was formed and established to support the exploration and gradual implementation of CCS in the Baltic Sea Countries. BASRECCS main activity is organisation of the annual Baltic Carbon Forum [17]. The main target of the BASRECCS is implementation of CCUS projects in the Baltic Sea Region. Participants from Poland and Lithuania are active in the BASRECCS and presented in the BASRECCS Board.

Financial Institutions

Funds for the implementation of projects and measures in Lithuania are available annually from the state and municipal budgets. EU funds, including the EU Structural and Investment Funds and other dedicated funding instruments (e.g. Connecting Europe Facility), as well as the National Climate Change Programme (CCP) and the Modernisation Fund, represent a significant part of energy and climate investments. Investments from the Innovation, Social Climate Funds, and the Next Generation Lithuania Plan (Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) can contribute to the achievement of the energy and climate objectives.

Project developers and partners

Project partners from Lithuania include Orlen Lietuva oil company, Achema chemical plant (the largest CO₂ producer in Lithuania), two power companies from Vilnius (Energijos Gamyba and Šilumos Tinklai), and three waste to energy plants, including two Fortum GREN plants from Vilnius and Kaunas and UAB Kauno WtE from Vilnius.

Orlen, Fortum (Gren) and Achema are the companies that are planning, interested, and developing CO₂ capture and CCUS projects for number of years. Achema provided CO₂ for injection experiments for CO₂ storage and CO₂-EOR successfully made in Lithuania in 2013 and 2015 by Minijos Nafta company [18].

Additional specific stakeholders are named in Table 4-5.

Table 4-5 List of stakeholders (Lithuania)

Name	Responsibility / Strategies	Action
Orlen	Polish multinational oil refiner, petrol retailer and natural gas trader headquartered in Plock, Poland is recently focusing on energy transition strategies, to become net zero by 2050. In Lithuania, Orlen owns the Orlen Lietuva refinery.	The company objectives include reduction of CO ₂ emissions & emissions intensity in the refinery, petrochemicals, and upstream segments through several actions. One example is the implementation of CCUS technologies, including the development of a CO ₂ terminal in Gdańsk (as a consortium leader; ECO2CEE PCI project) and industrial scale CO ₂ capture units. Because the company upstream assets include hydrocarbon E&P operators, storage in depleted hydrocarbon fields is planned as well.
Achema	Achema is a leading producer of nitrogen fertilisers and chemical products in Lithuania and the Baltic states. Achema is the largest CO ₂ producer in Lithuania.	Achema can capture CO ₂ during its chemical processes. Achema produced CO ₂ for the first CO ₂ injection experiments in the Baltic States made by Minijos Nafta company in 2013. Achema is interested in CCUS projects and participate in the annual Baltic Carbon Forum.

4.5 Italy

Regulatory authorities

In Italy, the MASE – Ministry of Environment and Energy Security are the competent authority for issuing storage permits (administrative). The technical evaluation of the project has been conducted by the ETC COMMITTEE. This is the National Committee for the Management of Directive 2003/87/EC and the support of Kyoto Protocol project activities.

Below the ETS COMMITTEE, there is a Technical Secretariat for underground CO₂ storage. This is a technical body within the ETS Committee for scientific and technical support in the evolution of storage projects. At the lowest level we have national scientific-technical bodies such as ISPRA – Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (TWG on CCS), INGV (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia; a research body) etc.

Figure 4-1 The exploration and storage CO₂ permits issuing the projects evaluation chain in Italy.

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

There are several non-governmental organisations active in Italy such as Carbon Gap LTC, Net Zero Tracker, and Clean Air Task Force.

Financial Institutions

The Italian state holds around a 30% stake in four key companies in the oil, gas, and electricity markets:

- Snam S.p.A, the Italian gas transmission system operator (TSO).
- Terna S.p.A., the electricity TSO.
- Eni, which is the largest player upstream, wholesale and retail sector.
- Enel, which accounts for the largest individual share of electricity production and over one-third of electricity sales.

The ENI-Snam partnership will start the first CCS project in Italy, with the CO₂ storage offshore in Ravenna, in the northern part of Italy.

Project developers and partners

Several carbon capture and storage projects are under development in Italy. The most important ones are Callisto Mediterranean CO₂ Network, Augusta CO₂ and the Prinos CO₂ project. Callisto with the Ravenna CO₂ storage hub and Prinos have received funding and been certified as EU Projects of Common Interest (PCI).

The CO₂ GeoNet organisations, which holds yearly meetings in Italy, have two Italian partners: OGS and SAPIENZA University of Rome. OGS -Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale, is an Italian national research institute, coordinating projects and international research initiatives in the field of oceanography and

experimental geophysics. Sapienza University of Rome focuses on researching gas migration mechanics and communication of research outcomes.

Additional specific stakeholders are listed in Table 4-6.

Table 4-6: List of stakeholders (Italy)

Name	Responsibilities
Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security	<p>Established in 2021 by folding responsibilities for energy, climate, and environmental into one ministry.</p> <p>The MiTE is also responsible for implementing environmental policy and promoting good environmental practices, including the promotion of climate education in schools.</p> <p>At the international level, MiTE holds a vital role in the management and distribution of EU funds. It aims to integrate energy and climate policies and advance the objectives of the green transition to a low-carbon economy in all the ministry's activities.</p>
Ministry of Transport, Infrastructure and Agriculture	Energy- or climate related competences.
The Ministry of University and Research (MUR)	Channels funds for energy research and developments.
The inter-ministerial Committee for Economic Planning and Sustainable Development (CIPESS)	<p>A collective governmental body chaired by the Prime Minister.</p> <p>Responsibilities include the cross-national coordination of policies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, govern overall research and innovation to ensure alignment with policy objectives, including the National Research Programme and public research institutions whose work is relevant to SDGs.</p>

4.6 Greece

Regulatory authorities

The regulatory authority in Greece is the Hellenic Republic Ministry of Environment and Energy.

In Greece, the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), [19], sets the national targets for 2030 on energy efficiency, renewables, and CO₂ emissions reduction, as well as energy security, interconnections, the single energy market and competitiveness, development, and sustainable mobility.

The recent law L.4920/2022 (art.228 par.1), as amended by L.4964/2022 (Article 175), designates the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the competent authority for the licensing, monitoring, and supervision of carbon storage projects. Moreover, Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduces a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economical operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas which could potentially be used for carbon storage [20].

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)

See Table 4-1.

Financial Institutions

EnEarth, a subcompany of the UK oil and gas company Energean has applied to the Hellenic Hydrocarbon and Energy Resources Management Company for a CO₂ licence in Prinos, offshore Greece [21].

Project developers and partners

According to the HERCCULES report D8.1 [22], two Greece projects have been approved for co-funding by the Innovation Fund:

- Iris project for CO₂ capture at the H₂ production plant of a refinery in Corinth.
- IFESTOS project for CO₂ capture in a cement plant in Viotia. IFESTOS involves the construction of a large-scale carbon capture facility at TITAN's flagship Kamari plant near Athens. TITAN will produce about 3 Mt/y of zero-carbon cement to serve the growing needs for green construction in the metropolitan area of Athens and beyond. Subject to regulation and permits, the carbon capture project will result in an absolute annual GHG emissions avoidance of more than 1.9 Mt/y of CO₂, making the Kamari plant one of the largest carbon capture facilities in Europe. It is estimated that the first phase (capacity of around 1 Mt/y CO₂) will be ready by the end of 2025 and the full capacity second phase (by the end of 2027).

5 Key insights for EU PCI Status Attainment

This section provides key insights on the application process for obtaining EU Projects of Common Interest (PCI) status. The guiding principle for securing EU PCI status is adherence to the Trans-European Networks for Energy (TEN-E) framework, which serves as the foundation for the application process. It is essential to ensure that the project meets the eligibility criteria, which typically include cross-border impact, enhancing market integration, improving security of supply, and contributing to sustainability. A few of these criteria were studied for specific project examples in a non-exhaustive method.

For CO₂ projects, the European Commission has allocated a special thematic PCI group, "CO₂ Networks," which is one of the priority groups. Highlighting the strategic importance of a particular CCUS project is important for securing PCI status. By emphasising its role in Europe's energy transition and contribution towards EU 2050 targets (European Commission, 2024), support can be gained from stakeholders and policymakers.

Another aspect of supporting a specific PCI application is demonstrating its technological readiness and viability, if possible.

Following the evaluation and recommendation by the regional groups – which consist of representatives from EU countries, including Transmission System Operators (TSOs), project promoters, national regulatory authorities, and others – in accordance with the specific PCI selection criteria under Article 4 of the TEN-E Regulation, the final decision is made by the European Commission. Successful projects are included in the PCI list, which is updated every two years.

We highlight four different leverages which are crucial for a successful PCI application:

- **Technical preparation:** displaying the project developer's experience and track record can be a particularly important asset to achieve the PCI status. This can also be achieved with partnerships with institutions holding relevant skills for the project development.
- **Stakeholders:** it is one of the most key factors to obtain a PCI status for a project. To ensure a sound project development, multiple entities must be brought onboards, as developers or external stakeholders. They can hold distinct roles or skills, contributing to the increase of the level of trust for the project completion.
- **Level of maturity:** the level of definition of the project is also an indicator of the project capability to achieve the PCI status. A well-defined concept, where multiple scenarios have been analysed and screened, facilitates the construction of a sound PCI application.
- **Financing:** while a PCI project facilitates the access to project funding, the applicants must show that they can raise the necessary funds to finance the project. This also means that it is important to have a solid economic analysis and business case.

The suggested PCI in section 3 follow different strategies with different requirements:

- The pipeline infrastructure from Germany to Denmark consists of a single pipeline to support a larger network. It is a crucial infrastructure to support carbon capture in the northern regions of Germany and the development of storage and utilisation initiatives in Denmark. This requires the involvement of multiple stakeholders, based in both countries.
- The pipeline infrastructure to Gdansk consists of a full network to enable CCUS value chains in the Baltic countries of Poland and Lithuania, with the possibility of extension to Czechia. Here, the infrastructure was not divided into smaller projects, which increases the level of difficulty in raising funds and requires the involvement of many stakeholders from different areas. It also leads to a more holistic development of the value chain, ensuring project continuity.
- The pipeline and harbour infrastructure in Italy and Greece considers an additional type of infrastructure: a harbour and onshore terminal. This creates a higher diversity of risks and challenges, but also opportunities, to obtain CO₂ shipped from longer distances such as France.

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7 Abbreviation List

Table 7-1 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	
ACER	Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CCP	Climate Change Programme
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CY	Cyprus
DK	Denmark
EC	European Commission
EL	Greece
EOR	Enhanced Oil Recovery
EPC	Engineering, Procurement and Construction
ES	Spain
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
FR	France
HC	Hydrocarbon
HR	Croatia
ICMS	Industrial Carbon Management Strategy
IT	Italy

Abbreviation	
kt	Thousand tonnes
LT	Lithuania
LV	Latvia
MRR	Monitoring and Reporting Regulation
Mt	Million tonnes
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NL	Netherlands
NO	Norway
NRA	National Regulatory Authorities
O&G	Oil and Gas
PCI	Project of Common Interest
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
T&S	Transport and Storage
TEN-E	Trans-European Network for Energy
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UK	United Kingdom
y	year
ZEN	Zero Emission Network (project)